

Synthesis of Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes including azobenzene and its application to mediators of laccase for biofuel cells

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Laccase is mainly used as an enzyme of a cathode electrode of a biofuel cell. One problem is rate limiting of electron transfer between electrodes and enzymes. To enhance transfer of electron from the electrode to the redox center in the enzyme, using mediators instead of substrates of laccase is one the solution. A selection of the mediator is important in improving the performance of the biofuel cell. Our laboratory has succeeded in improving the electron transfer function by controlling the polarization-induced molecular orientation of a complex having an azo dye in a laccase matrix. In this study, we will synthesize a mononuclear complex including azobenzene, a binuclear complex and a tetranuclear complex containing Cu^{II} or Mn^{II/III} ions, and evaluate how much multistep electron transfer and molecular orientation by multinuclear complex will contribute to function as a mediator.

Keywords: Azobenzene, Cu, Mn, oxygen reduction, laccase.

Introduction

Laccase is an enzyme that catalyzes four-electron reduction of oxygen, and oxygen is reduced through four copper atoms. Such a protein having a function including a copper atom is referred to as multicopper oxidase (MCO). MCO such as laccase is used as enzyme on the cathode side of enzyme type biofuel cell¹⁻⁶.

In addition, as an enzyme for dyeing waste water treatment, anthraquinone type and azobenzene type coloring matter are considered to be effective. The four copper atoms that are the active centers of the^{7,8} laccase are divided into three types, T1, T2 and T3, respectively, and T2 copper and two T3 copper form triple nuclear clusters (TNC). T1 Copper first receives electrons from the substrate and oxidizes the substrate, followed by 4-electron reduction at TNC⁹.

A low molecular weight redox substance (electron transfer mediator) is a substance that helps to give and receive electrons by being sandwiched between an enzyme and an electrode. It is known that in the enzyme type biofuel cell has a problem in transferring electrons between the enzyme and the

electrode. As a method for solving this, there are a method of using conductive nanowires to directly deliver electrons, a method of using metal nanoparticles, and a method of using the above-described electron transfer mediator. Metalloproteins such as laccase^{10,11} may be regarded as metal complexes having remarkably complicated peptide ligands. In particular, in the case of phenolate, thiolate, oxo and sulfide and *N*-heterocyclic chelates, the metal complex shows a very strong low energy charge transfer (CT) absorption band, reflecting highly covalently bound ligand-metal bond. These contribute greatly to the electronic structure of the active site, which may affect the geometry of the metal site and the orientation of the ligand-metal bond and the conformation of the protein^{12,13}. Often these sites are unique compared to small molecule copper complexes and exhibit spectral features derived from geometric and electronic structures on metal ions by interaction with protein biopolymers¹⁴. Since the electron transfer mediator is related not only to the reaction rate with the enzyme but also to the electron transfer rate between the mediators, the selection of the optimum mediator is one of the research subjects¹⁵.

Azobenzene is a photoresponsive organic compound that causes *cis-trans* isomerization by irradiation with ultraviolet light. Because of its properties, azobenzene is used as a photochromic dye, an organic/inorganic hybrid material with an inorganic coordination compound and an important technique for optical (magnetic) data recording^{16–21}. It is also known that molecular orientation can be induced by irradiating linear polarized ultraviolet light on a material in which azobenzene is dispersed in a polymer such as PMMA^{22,23}. In addition, changes in oxidation-reduction potential and current value due to polarized irradiation have been reported from previous studies and are subjects of research in various material fields^{24,25}.

In this research, in order to further improve the performance of the cathode electrode, we are looking for a mediator compatible with laccase. Moreover, by using a mediator including photoresponsive azobenzene, a conformational change due to photoisomerization occurs in laccase. In order to evaluate how it affects laccase, Schiff base metal complexes of **1**, **2**, **4** nuclei were synthesized²⁶. In mononuclear complexes, we also incorporated anthraquinone moieties that have been successful in the past²⁷. Polynuclear complexes have a wide range of redox potentials and can be expected as mediator performance²⁸. It is also aimed to examine the compatibility of laccase with the difference in the structure of the hydrophobic region and the molecular size.

Next, the electron transfer reaction caused by complexing of a protein and a metal complex as a ligand will be examined in detail from the molecular design of the metal complex. In the protein ligand complex system, if changes are observed by performing spectroscopic measurement, electrochemical measurement, etc., discussion will be made on complexation and the electron transfer mechanism of the mediator will be elucidated.

Schiff base is a generic term for compounds gen-

erated by dehydration reaction of aldehyde or ketone with a primary amine. Schiff base complexes are rich in coordination environment around the central metal, various studies such as steric effect of substituent, solid structure phase transition by temperature, conformation change in solution and solution paramagnetism have been conducted. In this study, the use of Cu^{II}, Mn^{II} as the central metal ion, alanine and 2-amino-anthraquinone as the amine and 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5-phenyldiazobenzaldehyde as the aldehyde makes it possible to obtain novel complexes that was synthesized (depicted in Figs. 1–3).

Fig. 1. Structures of complexes 1-2 (M = Mn, Cu).

Fig. 2. Structures of complexes 3-4 (M = Mn, Cu).

Fig. 3. Structures of complex 5.

Characterization of the compounds was carried out by yield, infrared absorption spectra, UV-Vis spectra, and single crystal X-ray structural analysis.

Experimental

General procedures:

Chemicals of the highest commercial grade available (solvents from KantoChemical, organic compounds from Tokyo Chemical Industry and metal sources from Wako) were used as received without further purification.

Preparation:

Preparations of complexes:

Diazo coupling with *o*-vanillin was carried out using aniline as a starting material. In addition, all of the experimental procedures in this section were performed under the condition of 0°C to 5°C. In a 200 mL Erlenmeyer flask, 15 mL of ion exchange water and 15 mL of hydrochloric acid were added, and 0.93 g (10 mmol) of aniline was slowly added dropwise thereto. Next, a solution of 0.69 mg (10 mmol) of sodium nitrite dissolved in 30 mL of ion-exchanged water was slowly added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 30 min. Thereafter, 1.52 g (10 mmol) of *o*-vanillin was added, the pH was adjusted to 7 using a 10 wt% sodium hydroxide aqueous solution, and the mixture was stirred for 30 min.

The solution was filtered and the resulting filtrate was washed with water. By drying, a reddish brown powder of the objective 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5-phenyldiazobenzaldehyde (hereafter abbreviated as Azo) was recovered, the yield was 1.72 g, and the yield was 67.5%. Characterization was carried out by NMR and the peak of aldehyde could be observed. (¹H NMR 400 MHz, CDCl₃: 10.04 (s, CHO)).

Azo (0.128 g, 0.5 mmol) and 2-aminoanthraquinone (hereafter abbreviated as Aq, 0.111 g, 0.5 mmol) were stirred at 313 K for 4 h in a 200 mL Erlenmeyer flask with 50 mL of methanol as a solvent. Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.122 g, 0.5 mmol) was added thereto, and the mixture was further stirred for 4 h. After stirring, methanol in the solvent was evaporated by evaporator and washed with water to obtain a reddish brown powder.

Similarly, a complex in which the metal origin was changed and a complex in which the amine portion was changed to aniline were synthesized. In the tetranuclear manganese complex, the stirring time was set to 2 h each, and crystallization was carried out in a methanol solution.

1: Yield 16.4%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1595s (C=N), 1672s (C=O), **2:** Yield 47.2%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1595s (C=N), 1671s (C=O), **3:** Yield 35.5%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1633s (C=N), **4:** Yield 16.3%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1637s (C=N), **5:** Yield 32.4%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1627s (C=N); μ = 1.25 B.M./mol (Mn ion) (300 K); Curie-Weiss: χ = C/(T - θ), θ = -7.185 K, C = 41.67 cm³ mol⁻¹ K; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): 1.60 ppm (6H, s), 4.03 ppm (2H, s), 7.26–7.54 ppm (4H, m), 7.76 ppm (4H, m), 7.91 ppm (4H, m), 10.05 ppm (2H, s).

Preparations of hybrid materials of complex (1-5)+laccase or PMMA:

Acetone solution (0.5 mL) of a complex (1-5) (0.0019 g in 5 mL acetone) and buffer solution (2 mL) of laccase were cast onto a slide glass to give rise to a film of hybrid materials 1+laccase through 5+laccase.

Acetone solution (0.5 mL) of a complex (1-5) (0.0019 g in 5 mL acetone) and acetone solution (2

mL) of polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) (10%) were cast onto a slide glass to give rise to a film of hybrid materials **1**+PMMA through **5**+PMMA.

Physical measurements:

Infrared spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a JASCO FT-IR 4200 plus spectrophotometer in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} at 298 K. Electronic spectra were measured on a JASCO V-570 UV/VIS/NIR spectrophotometer (equipped with an integrating sphere for diffuse reflectance spectra) in the range of 800–200 nm at 298 K. Electrochemical (cyclic voltammetry, CV) measurements were carried out on a BAS SEC2000-UV/VIS and ALS2323 system with Ag/AgCl electrodes range of –0.50 to 0.80 V vs Ag/Ag⁺. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL JMN-300 spectrometer (300 MHz) in CDCl₃. Photo-illumination were carried out using a lamp (1.0 mW/cm²) with optical filters (UV λ = 200–400 nm) leading to a sample by using optical fibers and polarizer through optical filters. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of a powder crystalline sample of **5** were carried out at a Quantum Design MPMS-XL superconducting quantum interference device magnetometer (SQUID) at an applied field 0.5 T in a temperature range 5–300 K. Powder samples were measured in a pharmaceutical cellulose capsule. The diamagnetic correction was carried out using Pascal constants²⁹.

X-Ray crystallography:

Reddish prismatic single crystals of **5** were glued on top of a glass fiber and coated with a thin layer of epoxy resin to measure the diffraction data. Intensity data were collected on a BrukerAPEX2 CCD diffractometer with graphite monochromated Mo K α radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). Data analysis was carried out with a SAINT program package. The structures were solved by direct methods with SHELXS-97³⁰ and expanded by Fourier techniques and refined by full-matrix least-squares methods based on F^2 using the program SHELXL-97³⁰. An empirical absorption correction was applied by a program SADABS³¹. All non-hydrogen atoms were readily

located and refined by anisotropic thermal parameters. All hydrogen atoms were located at geometrically calculated positions and refined using multiplication models.

Crystallographic data for 5 (CCDC 1824336): C₆₆H₆₈Mn₄N₈O₂₀, crystal size 0.69 mm × 0.092 mm × 0.083 mm, M_w = 834.75, triclinic, space group *P*-1, a = 9.262(4) Å, b = 12.351(6) Å, c = 15.705(7) Å, α = 68.679(6)°, β = 76.717(6)°, γ = 89.451(6)°, V = 1623.4(13) Å³, $\rho_{\text{calcd.}}$ = 1.546 g/cm³, μ = 0.843 nm⁻¹, $F(000)$ = 778.0, Goodness of fit = 1.046, $R_1[I > 2\sigma(I)]$ = 0.0642, wR_2 = 0.2001.

Results and discussion

Crystal structure of 5:

The molecular structure of **5** is depicted in Fig. 4, which was the only compound whose single crystal can be obtained. The complex **5** has a structure in which four Mn atoms are arranged in a plane and has a center of point symmetry. Also, the facing azobenzene moieties are in parallel with each other. In addition, the coordination structure around Mn adopts an incomplete double cubane structure.

Fig. 4. Crystal structures of **5** showing selected atom labeling scheme. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distance (Å) and bond angles (°): Mn1–Mn2 = 3.1334 (15), Mn1–Mn2ⁱ = 3.1468 (18), Mn1ⁱ–Mn2 = 3.1468 (17), Mn2–Mn1–Mn2ⁱ = 62.35(4), Mn1–Mn2–Mn1ⁱ = 117.65 (4), Mn2–O10–Mn1 = 101.92 (14), Mn2–O10–Mn2ⁱ = 99.77 (13), Mn1ⁱ–O10–Mn2ⁱ = 94.06 (14), Mn2–O9–Mn1ⁱ = 106.95 (17). Symmetric operation (i) (–x, –y, 2–z).

UV-Vis spectra:

UV-Vis measurement was carried out with 0.01 mM DMSO solution (shown in Fig. 5). Absorption

Fig. 5. Experimental (acetone solutions; red) UV-Vis spectra of 1-5.

at 220 to 320 nm due to π - π^* transition of azobenzene and anthraquinone was confirmed from UV-Vis spectrum of each complex. CT transition at around 400 nm could be also confirmed for each complex.

Polarized UV-Vis and IR spectra after linearly polarized UV light irradiation:

Also, in the polarized UV-Vis spectrum measurement, when the angle of the electric field vector of the measurement light parallel to the electric field vector of the irradiation light is 0° and the electric field vector of the vertical measurement light is 90° , absorption parallel to the incident polarized light A_0 , the absorption perpendicular to the incident polarized light is denoted as A_{90} , and the anisotropy parameter $R = A_0/A_{90}$ is calculated.

A change in absorbance was confirmed with the UV-Vis spectra. In addition, Table 1 compares the R value after irradiation with ultraviolet polarized light with the R value in the initial state (namely relative values to 0 min as standard) of the nuclear complex as **1**. As a result, the complete orientation in the vertical direction was not controlled, but the molecular motion due to the optical anisotropy of the azobenzene complex was observed from the change in R value. In addition, since the change in R value is greater for mononuclear complexes, orientation is likely to be easier.

Table 1. R values at before (initial) and after UV light irradiation for 10 min

	R (initial)	R (10 min)
1	0.724	2.113
2	0.816	1.231
3	1.528	1.090
4	1.540	1.131
5	1.044	0.978

Electrochemical behavior and photo-induced molecular orientation of a complex:

The copper complex prepared this time showed a series of Mn complexes as a remarkable decrease in current amount was confirmed by combination with laccase. In order to confirm the change in the amount of current in the Nafion[®] membrane, which is a flex-

ible place where the movement of molecules is restricted to some extent by the Weigert effect when irradiated with linearly polarized ultraviolet light. In this experiment, the complex system of laccase and **1** showed an increase in the amount of current with respect to the reduction current of oxygen. Therefore, it is considered that the complex **1** is the most effective as a mediator for these systems among **1-5**.

Docking calculation:

Complex and protein docking simulation was carried out using calculation software GOLD suite (ver. 5.5.0). From the Protein Data Bank, we obtained single crystal structure data 1GYC from Laccase from *Trametes versicolor* and used this to calculate how

Fig. 6. CV (scan rate 0.05 V s^{-1}) measured using RRDE electrodes for Nafion coated laccase and **1** through **1**, **2** and **5** materials. After polarized UV light for 0 (solid line) and 10 (dashed line) min and under O_2 atmosphere.

the complex behaves in the vicinity of the hydrophobic pocket at coordinates close to T1 copper (hereafter T denotes so-called “type” of copper proteins)³².

Since laccase supplies electrons from T1Cu and oxygen is reduced by T2T3Cu, it is desirable that the complex as a ligand intervenes between the electrode-T1 and functions as an electron mediator. Therefore, the calculation was calculated so as to join the coordinates around the coordinates such that it enters the hydrophobic region pocket including T1Cu [(x, y, z) = (14, 25, 32)].

The docking score of the **1** shows a value from about 16 to 55, and the **5** shows a wide value from -68 to 60. In addition, the distance between the complex and T1Cu was 6.320 \AA in Fig. 7 (right) and 7.641 \AA on Fig. 7 (left). The influence of van der Waals forces on both sides greatly influences the Fitness Score, and the aromatic rings, which are thought to cause this interaction, also result in that the distances on the left side are far apart.

Fig. 7. Docking simulation between **1** and laccase. (Left): Fitness Score = 19.38. (Right): Fitness Score = 53.85.

From this result, most of **1** would work as a mediator because it can exist in the vicinity of T1Cu. In addition, because the docking score of the **1** is high on average, the docking ability with laccase is also high, and it seems that the function as a mediator has been developed³³. Furthermore, in the case of **1** complexes with high docking scores, the complex distance to the central metal was close.

Therefore, according to docking simulation, polarized UV light irradiation resulted in photoisomerization to *cis* form as well as rotation of molecular

orientation due to Weigert effect of azo-containing complexes. This changes makes complexes to form good electron transfer path between electrode and laccase in the surface hydrophobic pocket of laccase. Suitable fitting of small complexes to laccase may be predominant factor rather than redox moieties such as multinuclear metal complexes or redox active moiety of ligands in this case.

Conclusions

In this experiment, complexes applicable as a mediator of an enzyme type biofuel cell was synthesized and physical properties were compared. In addition, the influence of orientation control in the complex-enzyme composite film was also compared. As a result, it was confirmed that the optical anisotropy increased after irradiation with linear ultraviolet light by the Weigert effect in the films. Moreover, the function of the complex as a mediator before and after molecular orientation was compared. It was not possible to confirm the increase in the amount of current before and after molecular orientation in the complex itself, but in the complex-enzyme complex system, the oxygen reduction peak was improved in the **1**. It is thought that this is due to the molecular orientation of the complex, as the complex approaches the copper atom which is the active site of laccase, the electrons are easily transferred. This can be inferred also from the fact that in the calculation by the docking simulation software GOLD Suite, the complex was closer to the active site in the case of a complex with a higher docking score due to molecular movement of the **1**. By doing this, we obtained new finding that improving the function as a mediator by performing molecular motion by light without destroying heat-sensitive laccase.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

CCDC 1824336, contains the supplementary crystallographic data for **5**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12, Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax: (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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